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AN EMPIRICAL INTERROGATION OF KARL DEUTSCH'S "SOCIAL MOBILISATION AND POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT" THESIS WITHIN THE NIGERIA'S CONTEXT

E. Chijioke Ogbonna

Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State,
Nigeria.

Nwamadi Bright C.

Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State,
Nigeria.

Abolaji Solomon

Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State,
Nigeria.

ABSTRACT: In 1968, Karl Deutsch published his widely accredited seminal on "Social Mobilisation and Political Development". According to Deutsch, 'social mobilisation' is a transformational process, especially a movement away from the traditional way of doing things to modern ways. Deutsch carefully crafted his indicators for social mobilization as follows: *Exposure to aspects of modern life, Exposure to mass media, Change of residence, Urbanization, Literacy and Change from agricultural occupations*. This work sets out to interrogate the relevance and applicability of same indicators as identified by Deutsch in Nigeria. Employing a mixed method involving systematic critique and content analysis that relies on secondary data, as well as descriptive survey method, using questionnaire administered to 700 respondents in 3 states of Nigeria (Enugu, Abuja and Lagos). Multi-stage sampling was adopted involving purposively mapping the country into 3 ethnopolitical zones (Eastern/Niger-Delta, Northern and Western), from which samples were selected in clusters. Data was analysed using percentage, mean and standard deviation. The study found that all indicators of social mobilizations are significance to Nigeria's political development, the top very critical indicator was exposure to mass media (TV, Radio, and Newspaper) and social media with the mean of 3.4 ± 0.8 on the scale of 4 points. This was followed closely by Availability and use of Mobile telephone & internet services and level of literacy with the mean of 3.3 ± 0.8 , other indicators include Ratio of Urban to rural dwellers with the mean 3.0 ± 0.9 while level of wealth accounted for the mean 2.7 ± 1.0 and change of residence in other regions order than yours with the mean of 2.8 ± 1.0 respectively. It therefore recommends an integrated approach in orientation/education of the citizens towards political relevance.

Keywords: Karl Deutsch, Social Mobilisation, Political Development, Nigeria.

Introduction

Political development in terms of citizens-driven governance through democratic forms is not a stand-alone process. In as much as it is citizens driven, the citizens are in turn conditioned by other social factors which enhance their dynamics as political 'animals'. The effort here includes tracking a relationship between the general citizenry as agents amenable to social factors which in turn impacts the political process and situating social

mobilisation as instrumental or majorly contributory in equipping the citizens in the democratic-political society to become critical. In this direction, Karl Deutsch's "Social Mobilisation and Political Development" thesis remain significant and an appropriate pillar in this study. Karl Deutsch (1968) appraises 'social mobilisation' as a transformational process, especially a movement away from the traditional way of doing things to modern ways.

The major concern in Deutsch seminal is that if these were mainly short term changes, it would have remained largely insignificant, but they are inextricably associated with larger economic and political implications. The implication of social mobilisation is not just a mere fancy of modernity but the induction process (involving large members of the community) usually associated with it. Social mobilisation has two stages with implications on any society as follows:

- First, the stage of uprooting or breaking away from old settings, habits and commitments;
- Second, the induction of the mobilized persons into some relatively stable new patterns of group membership, organisation and commitment (Deutsch 1968).

The process is characterized by a movement by people away from the life of local isolationism and political apathy, and moving into a broader and deeper life characterized by involvement in the vast complexities of modern life, including mass politics (Deutsch 1968 cf. Mannheim).

Nigeria as a country is experiencing its highest stretch in political development. It has experienced a period of 22 years uninterrupted democracy culminating in 61 electoral circles – the 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015, 2019 general elections, though with slight alterations in gubernatorial and other elections due to outcome of electoral litigations among others. More so, within this period, there has as well been an in such tools of social mobilisation like proliferation of mobile phones and burgeoning of smart phone devices and internet services giving the masses yet an option in political engagement. This, alongside other indicators is to be tested in this research

work drawing heavily from Karl Deutsch's indicators.

Statement of Problem

Karl Deutsch in about more than five (5) decades ago established a relationship between social mobilisation and political development. According to him 'social mobilisation' is a transformational process, especially a movement away from the traditional way of doing things to modern ways. His interest in social mobilisation stem from the understanding that the process was not a short term fuss but one with transformative destination. Deutsch articulated the indicators of social mobilization as follows: ***Exposure to aspects of modern life, Exposure to mass media, Change of residence, Urbanization, Literacy and Change from agricultural occupations.*** This work sets out to interrogate the relevance and applicability of same indicators as identified by Deutsch in Nigeria in the Nigerian context. It will merely expand this discourse by adding and reviewing few elements like the preponderance of teledensity.

Research Question

The work is set to interrogate the following question:

Are the indicators of Social Mobilization identified by Karl Deutsch relevant to Nigeria's Political Development?

Literature Review

Social mobilisation and Political Development

Social mobilization from the perspective of Deutsch (1968) has to do with how the citizens move away from the traditional way of doing things to modern ways of doing things. Social mobilisation here transmutes and equips 'traditional' and unexposed citizens into active roles in the political development process and

especially prepare them for the necessary role of policing governance. Therefore, while democracy is favored as the best of all the tested systems of government especially with regards to its implication for development, it is its people-centeredness which allows for the achievement of the good of the greater agenda in a democratic state through electing their representatives and mobilizing against undesirable policies, through public opinion, which are largely influenced by their level of social mobilization, that gives democracy its comparative advantage. To this extent, the most favored idea of political development has long been seen from the lens of democracy. The public sets the agenda in a democratic state through electing their representatives and mobilizing against undesirable policies, through public opinion, which are largely influenced by their level of social mobilization.

How much of social mobilisation, especially with regards to its implications on political development (democratization) depends on certain prime indicators as provided by Deutsch (1968). The efficacy of the relationship between social mobilisation and democratisation lies as what has been theoretical captured by Seymour Martin Lipset in what he had earlier been put as the social prerequisite of democracy (Lipset, 1959). It is a fact that, “apart from people's ability to act and desire to engage, the roots of political action may also rest within the opportunities offered by the political environment” (McAtee and Wolak 2011:47).

Indicators of Social Mobilisation relevant to Political Development

The indicators of social mobilisation are herein discussed as follows:

Exposure to aspects of modern life

There is varied interpretation to modern life which has deep rooted impact in the political man. Modern life is usually depicted through demonstrations of machinery, buildings, installations, consumer goods, and show windows, governmental, medical or military practice. As mundane as it appears, modern life has a critical composite relationship with democratisation. This singular indicator of social mobilisation sums up other remaining six indicators. For instance, the depiction of modern life through life style goes farther to enshrine other elements such as exposure to mass media, change of residence, urbanization, movement away from agricultural occupations, literacy and per capita income are all elements of one pack – ‘modern life’.

The relationship between mobilisation and democratisation is provided by Welzel and Inglehart (2008:134) thus:

Modernization tends to bring both cognitive mobilization and growing emphasis on self-expression values. This in turn motivates ever more people to demand democratic institutions and enables them to be effective in doing so as elites watch the costs of repression mount... modernization increases the probability that democratic institutions will emerge.

According to Kaviraj (2017). Modern societies are constantly engaged in devising more effective and expanded forms of collective agency.

Exposure to mass media

Mass media is another indicator of social mobilisation identified by Deutsch. Mass media enables information to be passed to a wider audience. It allows for debates, and airing of alternative options. When the majority of the citizens are exposed to mass media, information could easily be

passed to a very large audience, while the citizens could in turn use same to get to government or make a stand for or against government. Mass media enables government to inform the citizens of its decision and also for the citizens to inform government of their needs. Mass media is essentially a tool of political inclusion, debate, and audit and interest articulation. While the availability and exposure to mass media by a greater number of the citizens has serious implications on their level of political activism vis-à-vis democratisation, media ownership too have come to matter also. Powerful governments more often than not try to turn government owned media outfits to both their Public Relation tool and even propaganda machine. It therefore becomes clearer than a liberalized media sector with both public and private participation may create the expected equilibrium. This is critical as alternative idea is vital for successful and healthy democratisation.

Change of residence

Change of residence from one province, district or geopolitical zone to the other in a very large and variegated country by a larger percentage of the citizenry depicts two things; a dosage of education about the other groups order than your own; second, a wholesome acceptance for co-habitation to a point of melting of the distinct peoples into a nation-state. Change of residence allows for the development of affective political culture. For instance, one who changed residence can be able to compare and possibly mobilize his/her resident community towards citizen-centered government if hitherto that has been the norm of the political zone where he comes from, vice versa. As conceived by Lerner (1958), modern society requires modern personality capable of adapting to rapid

change and such feature characterized by empathy which suggests the general capacity to see oneself in the other fellows situation whether favorable or unfavorable. Change of residence, carries with it a psychological situation which has implications on the willingness of a person to accept other peoples' viewpoint – in essence tolerance and accommodation of dissent.

Urbanization

In as much as the indicator for the measurement of urbanization varies from country to country; however, large scale urban growth has implications on creating what could rightfully be referred to as urban culture. Of course, urbanization has a high degree of socio-economic element on one hand and on the other presupposes certain level of literacy about politics and government. While urban life throws up peculiar challenges, the urban dwellers have certain level of education about their rights, understanding of symbols and monuments, and the purpose of government and these in turn conditions their relationship with government. Urbanization also entails the availability of other elements facilitative of democratisation such as mass media, social networks, professional associations, neighborhood associations, social clubs, trade unions, etc. Also urbanization comes with the existence and predominance of wage earners, radio listeners, television audience, and subscribers to mobile internet. More recently, attendance to town hall meetings, that members uses to air their views about their needs and pressurize for the transformation of the political space.

Change from agricultural occupations

Agricultural occupation here approximates subsistence farming and village dwelling which descends (the

subsistence agrarian) actors to a zone of political isolation devoid of the appropriate networking for contributions in the democratisation process. Subsistence farmers are village dwellers who are 'tradition-bound' and politically irresponsible/apathetic. When these village dwellers are uprooted from the zone of intellectual isolation into 'centers' of 'networking' their needs changes, their understanding of the import of politics as well as their readiness and equipping to be inducted into politically responsive life.

Literacy

Literacy is the lifeline of active political participation. Being politically literate empowers the citizens with a formidable participatory potential in the democratisation process. Literacy allows the citizens to be able to understand and construe politics, political symbols and institutions. As well as to make rational and informed decisions about politics.

Change from agricultural occupations

The higher the per capita income, the more the evidence of increasing wealth among the citizenry which spills over most of the other indices of social mobilisation. Per capita income is the wealth of a state measured in terms of its Gross National Product (GNP) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Aside these indicators as provided by Deutsch (1968), such other factors like teledensity – the ratio of mobile phone owners in a locality – and even the ability of mobile telephony to traverse the hitherto inauspicious zones are contemporary key factors in social mobilisation. The availability and use of internet, the accommodation of such function in smart phones, coupled with a variety of functions which the mobile phones now has. Of moment here, is social

media apps as well as orthodox media providing a social media pathways too and developing mobile apps which are accommodated on smart phones.

Theoretical Framework

The "social prerequisites for democracy" thesis implies that political development does not operate in a vacuum. It is a product of salient environmental factors. It is conditioned by certain social elements. It is in this frame that scholars often talk about 'favorable' and 'unfavorable' conditions of democratisation. There are two pathways to the discourse on social pre-requisites of democracy in the literature – the comparative normative theses and the Empiricists' work. The comparative-normative works are those of Huntington (1991), Beetham (1994), Weingast (1996), etc; and the empiricists' work are those of Lipset (1959), Deutsch (1968), etc. The foci of these works have been on such elements as the impact of ethnicity, religion, political culture, the economy, and political institutions. More yielding to empirical analysis are such elements as literacy/education, mass media, and the factors pertaining to the differentiation in levels of economic circumstances (per capita income and industrialization); although some of the theoretical postulations concerning these go considerably back in time. For example, as far as Aristotle's time, political theorists had long recognized that conditions of acute class differences, income inequality, and chronic poverty impede the establishment and growth of democracy. Most research works on conditions of democracy are mostly comparative, especially between the socio-economic conditions of advanced democracy and cross examining findings with the realities of evolving and new democracies.

The need for socio-economic conditions of

democracy is based on the following characteristics of a democratic political system as observed by Lipset (1959); first is collective responsibility of the ruling and the opposition to political authority; second, is the periodic awarding of political authority absence of which would result in irresponsible government, third, is the proposition that lack of opposition leads to maximization of power and minimization of popular influence on policy typical of one party states. In essence, economic development and legitimacy are intertwined as having a casual linkage in this discourse.

The focus on economic development has been on the elements of wealth, industrialization, urbanization, education, etc. as being critical social factors in democracy. As observed:

From Aristotle down to the present, men have argued that only in a wealthy society in which relatively few citizens lived in real poverty could a situation exist in which the mass of the population could intelligently participate in politics and could develop the self-restraint necessary to avoid succumbing to the appeals of irresponsible demagogues (Lipset 1959: 75).

The above assumption is not far from Ake's (1996) aphorism that "it is true that man does not live by bread alone. But it is a more fundamental truth that man cannot live without bread". Therefore when a society has strong differentials along the line of few elite and large impoverished mass, dictatorial rule is bound to subsist. While this thesis is in principle a fact, it cannot however be the condition for all circumstances. For instance, certain historical conjectures could resurrect an unanticipated reaction to the *rule of governance*. Also, a study of revolutions has proved that societal

inequities are not inelastic but a limit after which the masses would revolt and demand a change at a price higher than non-revolutionary transition away from authoritarian rule.

Another subsisting thesis within the economic development paradigm is the conjecture about a pre-existing middle class as occupying a vital position in democracy. The understanding is that ownership of property warrants an interest in politics. Associated with this thesis is Marx's proposition that "only those who have nothing to lose ever revolt" (Tocqueville 1945: 258). The middle class owns property and always wish to protect/preserve and increase their property and not necessarily for the love of country. There is an observation by Fukuyama (2012) that the "middle class people do not necessarily support democracy in principle: like everyone else, they are self-interested actors who want to protect their property and position". Significantly, while the middle class are resourceful to democracy and forming and gaining memberships in trade unions and professional associations and other spectrum of civil society organisations; in countries like China and Thailand, many middle class groups have been found supporting authoritarian governments in order to protect their property.

Education is another vital social requirement discussed as powerful tool and needed by citizens in order not only to become good citizens, but also for broadening their outlook (Dewey, 1916). Education enables citizens to "understand the need for norms of tolerance, restrains them from adhering to extremist and monistic doctrines, and increases their capacity to make rational electoral choices" (Lipset 1959). One major perception is that countries having more educated/literate citizens tend also to be

more susceptible to democratic rule than those with fewer educated citizens. Illiteracy not only provides an enablement for apathy, it could also furnish a ready audience to pick up pedestrian and even extreme ideologies. There is however a functional interdependence of industrialization, modernization, urbanization and education as all tends to produce spill-over effects on each other.

While Lipset (1959) himself acknowledged that there could be certain cases disproving his hypothesis on positive correlation between education and democracy, he adjudged such cases exemption that by no means make a rule. However, one flaw of his hypothesis, especially in recent times and in Africa is the postulation that “all relevant studies indicate that education is far more significant than income or occupation” (Lipset 1959). Ake’s (2008) thesis of functional relationship between class and education counteracts Lipset’s hypothesis. He posited:

Those from economically privileged groups tend to be better educated, ‘more cultured’, to have a higher social status, to be more ‘successful’ professionally and politically. This means that economic inequality is extremely important tending to reproduce itself endlessly in a series of inequalities (Ake, 2008:2).

Lipset’s (1959) focus on empirical data made him to overlook the normative analytical correlation between occupation, income, and education itself in a capitalist state. Of course, education is capital intensive in countries like Nigeria and other Third World countries and requires income to attain. Content and cost are therefore the biggest problem to education

in this regard. For instance, a critical question could be put up: what of if political apathy is far-fetched from lack of education and resurrected by the imposition of form of government alien to the people? What about when the educated citizens value themselves as capital too valuable to risk challenging an authoritarian regime?

The end product of the causal relationships of economic development and democracy is the construction of legitimacy. Legitimacy is associated with the perception as well as beliefs that convinces a political being into obedience of a political authority and system as representative of popular will and therefore effective. Effectiveness is the extent to which the citizens conceive political institutions and actual performance by government as satisfactory and the ability of such to restrain threat from powerful groups that could over-run the system. Where a variety of social exchange leads to the establishment of a structure which offers the stabilization of a political system, such an exchange could correlate political effectiveness.

Methodology

The research is a mixed research and adopted descriptive survey. The population of this study comprised of Members of Organised Intelligentsia, Organised Labor, Religious Leaders, Women Leaders, Social Media Actors/NGOs, Student Activist as well as other groups like farmers and artisans categorized as general public. The sample size is 700 arrived at using the formula and scale provided by the National Education Association, USA 1970, Krejcie & Morgan, (1970). The sample size was drawn from the 36 states and FCT in 6 geopolitical zones. The qualitative data were document based materials like

journals, textbooks and other secondary sources. The quantitative data were derived from the use of structured questionnaire, which involved adapting and modifying Deutsch's indicators of social mobilisation and testing same in field work. Adopting multi-stage sampling, three states of the federation representing each ethno-political group – Eastern Region/Niger-Delta, Western Region and Northern Region/FCT were purposively selected. Cluster sampling and purposive sampling were both used to draw the following number of respondents: Enugu 200 respondents, Abuja 200 respondents, and Lagos 300 respondents. Naturally, such sample elements like organised intelligentsia, organised labor, youth activists, select social media actors and NGOs were drawn from institutional clusters like tertiary

institutions, NGOs and other various bodies. The justification for the selection of the two states and FCT here lies on the factors which the zones evince, which includes:

- Hotbeds of civic actions,
- Represent regional or discernable political capital of some sort,
- Manifest additional attribute of being centers of political interest articulation, and
- Centers for the convening of active social movement.

The quantitative data was analysed using percentage, mean and standard deviation, while the document-based secondary sources were analysed using content analysis.

Table 1: Demographic Spread of Respondents

Parameters	Classification (N= 700)	Percentage
	Western region /Lagos	53.4
Region	Eastern Region/Niger Delta – Enugu	26.5
	Northern region/FCT – Abuja	20.1
	Total	100
Gender	Male	52.3
	Female	47.7
	Total	100
Age in years	18-27	59.1
	28-37	24.3
	38-47	10.1
	48-57	4.5
	58-67	2.0
	Total	100
Highest Qualification	BSc/HND	33.6
	Undergraduates	31.3
	MSc/MA/PGD	12.9
	SSCE	8.0
	OND	7.8
	PhD	3.8
	Up to JSS3	2.7

	Total	100
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Source: Field Survey, 202

identified by Deutsch relevant for establishing the efficacy of critical citizenry in democratisation?

Presentation of Result

Are the indicators for social mobilisation

Table 2: Descriptive analysis of Indicators of Social Mobilization relevant to Nigeria's Political Development

Indicators of social mobilization applicable	Very Applicable	Applicable	Somewhat Applicable	Not Applicable	Mean	SD
Exposure to Mass media and social media	54.7	35.8	5.3	4.2	3.4	0.8
Availability and use of Mobile telephone & internet services	49.0	37.6	7.7	5.7	3.3	0.8
Level of literacy	43.2	42.3	11.8	2.7	3.3	0.8
Ratio of Urban to rural dwellers	32.4	38.7	20.9	8.1	3.0	0.9
Level of Wealth	27.1	30.7	30.5	11.7	2.7	1.0
Knowledge & Residency in other regions order than yours	25.6	42.0	17.1	15.3	2.8	1.0

Key: means of 4 = Very Critical, 3 = Critical, 2 = Somewhat Critical, 1 = Not Critical

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Table 2: shows that of all indicators of social mobilization are significant and applicable to Nigeria's political development, the top very applicable indicator were exposure to mass media (TV, Radio, and Newspaper) and social media with the mean of 3.4 ± 0.8 on the scale of 4 points. This was followed closely by Availability and use of Mobile telephone & internet services and level of literacy with the means of 3.3 ± 0.8 , other indicators include Ratio of Urban to rural dwellers with the mean 3.0 ± 0.9 while level of wealth accounted for the mean 2.7 ± 1.0 and knowledge & residency in other regions order than yours with the mean of 2.8 ± 1.0 respectively.

Discussion of Findings

The indicators for social mobilisation here adopted domesticated those indicators measured by Deutsch's (1968) study about "social mobilisation and political development". However, within the present sociological context and especially given the dynamics of same after nearly five decades since his own study. Social elements like 'social media' and teledensity in the sense of the inquest into the general perception with regards to the availability and use of mobile telephones are now new elements influencing civic engagement and enjoys currency as even most subscribed routes by wide array of scholars ((Axford and Huggins 2001) Benkler (2006), Sunstein (2008), Castells (2010 and 2012)), and Dahlgren (2014) Ratto and Deibert (2014)). Indicators for social mobilisation are relevant for establishing the efficacy of

critical citizenry in democratisation. The findings thus revealed that majority of the respondents considered social mobilization very relevant for establishing the efficacy of critical citizenry in democratization process in Nigeria. That is, the finding shows a high level of acceptance among the respondents on the significance of social mobilisation in a sustainable critical citizenry in democratisation. Based on the responses, “Exposure to Mass media (TV, Radio, Newspaper, etc) and social media (Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, BBM, Online News and Blogs, etc)” ranked the most critical. No wonder, Lagos which is the media hub of Nigeria is also a center for aggregation and social networking for political change in contemporary Nigeria with more than 25 TV and radio stations, higher engagement and subscription to mobile telephony (NBS 2012). Availability and use of Mobile telephone & internet services and Level of literacy received the second highest approval. A combined implication of the findings is in agreement with scholarly postulations on the advent and import of a ‘new media’ (Axford and Huggins 2001) and new platform of civic engagement (Ratto and Deibert 2014). More significantly, the traditional media has also found a compatibility route by also providing a social media option. Invariably, the validity of the findings lies even deeper in proving the relationship between exposure to media with availability and use of mobile phones and internet services. Between the former and the later Sassi (2001) had established that the capacity to strike the formation of social bonds and networks for grass root mobilizing are mediated on the platforms made possible by the internet.

Respondents also concurred with selected theorists that education matters in political development and as such a

critical indicator. It is novel to note that the relationship between education and good governance was observed eve a century ago as powerful tool and needed by citizens in order not only to become good citizens, but also for broadening their outlook (Dewey, 1916). In reference to, Lipset (1959), Education enables citizens to “understand the need for norms of tolerance, restraints them from adhering to extremist and monistic doctrines, and increases their capacity to make rational electoral choices”. As such, a major perception is that countries having more educated/literate citizens tend also to be more susceptible to democratic rule than those with fewer educated citizens. This may also be the case among the different groups/regions that make up a badly divided society. Education empowers other forms of social engagement and even provides possible bonding routes which could graduate to social networks by such social options made possible through schooling like course mates, student associations, old boys, old girls etc. Illiteracy not only provides an enablement for apathy, it could also furnish a ready audience to pick up pedestrian and even extreme ideologies.

Ratio of Urban to rural dwellers was rated above wealth and knowledge and residency in other regions order than yours in badly divided societies. Urban dwelling is argued to plant the citizen into zone of political inclusion and high civic responsibility. Urban life throws up peculiar challenges, the urban dwellers have certain level of education about their rights, understanding of symbols and monuments, and the purpose of government and these in turn conditions their relationship with government. Urban centers are natural host to a variety of social networks. This could be understood

from the angle that urbanization also entails the availability of other elements facilitative of democratisation - first, availability of high resource for political engagement, such as mass media, radio, newspapers, etc. With Lagos hoisting of the highest number of media houses in Nigeria, it has been able to host a flourishing culture of social networking and mobilisation for change, despite not being the capital of Nigeria. High bandwidth for internet services, social networks, professional associations, neighborhood associations, social clubs, trade unions, etc are those traditional features of urban centers that is facilitative of critical citizenry vis-à-vis democratisation. There is no doubt that urbanization comes with the existence and predominance of wage earners, radio listeners, television audience, and subscribers to mobile internet. More recently, attendance to town hall meetings, that members uses to air their views about their needs and pressurize for the transformation of the political space.

With regards to the respondent perception on the 'Level of Wealth', the relationship between wealth and democratisation has always ranked secondary in previous studies like that of Lipset (1959), but agreed to be significant. The reality is that the impact of wealth on democratisation is on a direct correlation but works and influences other factors. For instance, mobile telephone services/internet and use of social media or subscription to media generally, urban dwelling are all hinged on class. According to Ake (2008); Those from economically privileged groups tend to be better educated, 'more cultured', to have a higher social status, to be more 'successful' professionally and politically. This means that economic inequality is extremely important tending to reproduce itself endlessly in a series of inequalities.

Education also in Nigeria comes at a cost, so if people must be sufficiently educated, it would cost money, and usually capital intensive too.

Knowledge and Residency in other regions order than yours had only 15.3% respondent's indifference, while the remaining 84.7% agreed to its importance though in varying degrees. In agreement with Lerner (1958), the significance of this is that modern societies requires modern personality capable of adapting to rapid change and such feature characterized by empathy which suggests the general capacity to see oneself in the other fellows situation whether favorable or unfavorable. Change of residence, carries with it a psychological situation which has implications on the willingness of a person to accept other peoples' viewpoint - in essence tolerance and accommodation of dissent.

Conclusion

Karl Deutsch's Social mobilisation indicators are relevant in the Nigerian context the efficacy of critical citizenry. The top very applicable indicator was exposure to mass media (TV, Radio, and Newspaper) and social. This was followed closely by Availability and use of Mobile telephone & internet services and level of literacy. The other indicators include Ratio of Urban to rural dwellers and knowledge & residency in other regions order than yours.

Conclusively, the 21st century upsurge in information and communication technology vis-à-vis social media revolution remain part of those evolutionary transition in human sociology that has strengthened democratisation globally. If transformation of authoritarian regime is not necessarily achieved by means of their overthrow, but may also result from the

processes of evolutionary change (Martins 1986), which mainly centers on the capacity of the citizens to insist on people-centered government as an irreducible value of governance, social networking through social media is the fiercest correspondent of this.

The study recommends an expansion of the political space must be sustained through the dynamics of social mobilisation to include the special population with a variety of impairments. Information communication technology (ICT) aids have proved useful in engaging thousands of citizens with a variety of impairments and limitations, and should be extended for use in electoral participation of this special sector. The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) should be involved in the provision and training of citizens with impairment on the use of ICT tools for political engagements.

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